

Kalikant Mishra*

Importance of Forensic Audit in Controlling Non-Performing Assets in Banks

Abstract

In the last two decades, a large number of scams, frauds and scandals have rocked the business fraternity across the world. The accounting scandals or manipulations in the books of accounts have led to big frauds like Enron, WorldCom, Madoff, Satyam, etc....This has created a crisis of confidence in the financial reporting practice and the effectiveness of 'Corporate Governance' in large companies. This has clearly demonstrated a failure of statutory audit in preventing and reducing misappropriation of corporate funds. This has resulted in an increase in corporate crimes, which in turn have put considerable pressure on the professional accountants and legal practitioners. A nationwide survey conducted by Kessler International concluded that this problem could be reduced by adopting Forensic Accounting or Forensic Audit by companies or organizations, worldwide.

Introduction

Indian companies are notorious for inflating project costs. A bunch of bankers, (into whose ears the political leadership and ministry minds whisper compelling advice) accept inflated project costs and sanction loans much larger than would be warranted if the project cost were realistic. While implementing the project through captive companies, the promoter then pilfers money out from the project funds, to line his own pocket and, also pay off the 'neta-babu' nexus or politicians, who were the reason for the inflated projections in the first place. Now, the project (whose actual cost is much lower) has to service a loan larger than what its viability warranted. The solution then is to set up yet more companies with inflated project costs and use these loan proceeds to service the original debt. A vicious circle is thus set up, that drains the money out of our

* **The author**, a managerial level employee in the State Bank of India, is having more than 30 years of managerial experience in Banks; he is an Alumni of IIT Roorkee and IIM Ahmedabad.

system to line the pockets of a few nefarious elements in our existing political system. If the process can be sustained until the original project becomes completely debt free and turns into a cash cow (a source of income) to service the subsequent rounds of loans, the promoter would have pulled off the project successfully. But, he has to repeat the process with the subsequent loans as well.

If this chain of recycling bank funds is broken before enough projects turn debt free and ready to finance the remaining loans, things turn sour. Multiple loans turn unserviceable. “During the period of aggressive lending from 2008 to 2014, the gross advances of Public sector banks increased by about Rs.34 lakh crores, from Rs.18.16 lakh crores to 52.15 lakh crores in 2014. It is also observed that despite repayment not being regular on these, through relaxation in loan classification, banks continued to keep defaulters as non-NPA account holders by restructuring them.” (FM Arun Jaitley, speaking in the FICCI conference at New Delhi, TOI, 29 November 2017).

Forensic Audit – Need of the Hour

This problem of the generation of non-performing assets could have easily been avoided if banks had opted for forensic audits in order to verify the end use of funds. The often-quoted reason, by Banks, for the creation of non-performing assets is inefficiency in the credit assessment and the credit management of a particular loan. This is evident from the diversion of funds, inflation of project costs and opening of shell companies by promoters. But, this could have easily been detected earlier, through *forensic audit as this audit actually verifies cash flow of the company with the help of the Company's bank's account statements and not just by relying on projected balance sheets of the company.*

“This ‘Forensic Audit’ also checks credit worthiness and other antecedents of bidders in the resolution plans under IBC. The conducting of the forensic audit of the bidder under Bankruptcy Code is essential to rule out the possibility of any fraud perpetrated by the promoters. In case of no fraud, genuine promoters may be allowed to proceed for insolvency proceedings or bid for stressed assets and in situations of fraud or siphoning of funds, the promoters may be charged and misappropriated funds may be recovered. The Forensic Audit is also a risk-mitigation strategy for IRP” says V. Dinkar, Partner (restructuring) at EY India. (ET, 13 November 2017) Nowadays, no lender wants to take any risks and a forensic investigation is just one of the things that could and should be done in the situation.

As non performing assets have been growing exponentially, among Indian banks, in the last few years, especially in the years 2012-2017; the Supreme Court has also expressed serious concern about this matter. During several hearings of many legal petitions and PILs filed against Big Corporate Houses, the Court has asked the concerned Ministry/departments/banks to initiate Forensic Audit of certain companies to verify whether the funds have been diverted by the promoters/directors for their own personal use. (ET, 12 December 2017).

Reserve Bank of India has asked Banks to conduct Forensic Audit of all 28 NPA accounts referred by it for resolution, to ensure that the end use of the lenders' funds is appropriate and they are utilised for the purpose for which these have been taken. Hence, Forensic Accounting or Audit is getting more and more importance while handling NPAs or Money laundering cases.

Forensic Audit or Accounting

Joshi (2003) gave the credit for the origin of forensic accounting to Kautilya, (the first economist to openly recognize the need for the forensic accountant) who mentioned 40 ways of embezzlement centuries ago. Crumbley (2001) stated that a form of forensic accounting can be traced back to an 1817 court decision. He also stated that a young Scottish accountant issued a circular advertising his expertise in arbitration support in 1824.

But, Maurice E. Peloubet is probably the first to publish the phrase *finance accounting* in his 1946 essay "*Forensic Accounting: Its Place in Today's Economy.*"

Forensic Accounting is a combination of two words—forensic and accounting. Forensic means suitable for use in a court of law. Accounting is the system of recording, summarizing, analyzing, verifying business and financial transactions and reporting the results thereof. Hence, in plain words, Forensic Accounting utilizes accounting, auditing and investigating skills to conduct an examination into a company's financial statements thus providing an accounting analysis that is suitable to present in court.

According to AICPA (American Institute of Chartered Public Accountants), "Forensic Accounting is the application of accounting principles, theories, and disciplines to facts or hypotheses at issues in a legal dispute and encompasses every branch of accounting knowledge." Harty defined forensic accounting as, "The Science that deals with the relation and application of finance, accounting, tax, and auditing knowledge to analyze, investigate, inquire, test and examine

matters in civil law, criminal law and jurisprudence in an attempt to obtain the truth from which to render an expert opinion.” (Bhasin 2007).

Forensic science according to Crumbley (2003), “may be defined as application of the laws of nature to the laws of man.” The science in question here is accounting science, meaning that the examination and interpretation will be of economic information.

Joshi (2003) defined Forensic Accounting as the application of specialized knowledge and specific skills to stumble upon the evidence of economic transactions. Zysman (2001) put Forensic accounting as the integration of accounting, auditing, and investigating skills. Simply put, forensic accounting is accounting that is suitable for legal review offering the highest level of assurance and including the now generally accepted connotation of having been arrived at in a scientific fashion. (Crumbley 2006) Coenen (2005) stated that forensic accounting involves the application of accounting concepts and techniques to legal problem. “Investigative and forensic accounting engagements’ are those that:

- require the application of professional accounting skills, investigative skills and an investigative mindset, and
- involve disputes or anticipated disputes or where there are risks, concerns or allegations of fraud or other illegal or unethical conduct.” (Canadian Institute of Chartered Accountant 2006)

There are separate bodies of Forensic Accountants spread all over the world like National Association of Forensic Accountants, American College of Forensic Examiners, Certified Forensic Financial Analyst CPA society, etc.

In the USA, the Sarbanes—Oxley Act (SOA) of 2002, has forced top management to certify that financial statements are free of frauds and material misstatements. Similar is the situation prevalent in India. As per clause 49 of the BSE/NSE listing requirements, companies have to give similar certificates to stock exchanges.

In India, after modification of Companies act, section 235 and section 237 deals with Forensic Audit and in case of large numbers of non-performing assets and shell companies, the Banks have started Forensic Audits to verify whether there is a possibility that funds have been diverted from the companies, by their promoters, for their personal use.

Main Steps in Forensic Analysis

- Data collection

- Data preparation
- Data analysis
- Reporting

For example, forensic analysis is used to review diversion of funds by verifying end use of funds. It is used in case of suspected embezzlement or fraud, to determine tax liability, to investigate allegations of bribery among other reasons.

The financial audit work would check whether, there has been misuse of the book of accounts, funds, including facilitation of accommodation entries or compromise of minority shareholder interest if any.

A forensic auditor examines a company's system of internal controls to identify any weakness in the control, designed to safeguard assets and to determine whether anyone in the company has exploited control weaknesses to misappropriate assets for personal gains.

Asset theft fraud occurs using one's position in a company usually as an employee to deliberately misuse or steal company's resources or assets for personal gain. Forensic Audit helps in detecting diversion of funds, wilful defaults and window dressing of financial statements. "With the rise in money laundering and wilful defaults cases, RBI has made forensic audit mandatory for large advances and restructuring of accounts. As per RBI, "The reasons for frauds include gap in credit underwriting standards, liberal cash flow projection at the proposal stage, lack of continuous monitoring of cash flow and cash profits (EBITDA) and lack of security perfection. The other reasons are over valuation, gold plating of projects, diversion of funds, double financing and general governance issues in banks." (*Economic Times*, 18 September 2017—PTI News quoting senior officials of RBI)

The Enforcement Directorate and the Serious Fraud Investigation Office (SFIO) under Ministry of Company Affairs, GOI have underscored the need for forensic audit following the rise in money laundering and wilful defaults cases that are plaguing the banking system.

The enactment of the 'Benami Property Act' increases the importance of Forensic audit in the country's fight against financial offenders. (Economic Times, 20 February 2017).

Reasons for the Creation of Present Day NPAs in Banks

- "Deficiencies in evaluation can be somewhat compensated for by careful post lending monitoring, including careful documentation and perfection of collaterals as well as ensuring assets backing; the promoter

guarantees are thus registered and tracked. *Unfortunately, too many projects were left weakly monitored even as costs increased.*

- The socialistic past led to the Indian Banks lending with compassion.
- Borrowers managed to exploit the fear of loss, which existed in the Banker's mind to their advantage and benign lenders fell into the trap and waited for the tide to lift the failed business. (Raghuram Rajan, ET, 21 June 2017).
- The role for the banks in mature markets is to originate loans and then distribute to other willing players in the market. (S.S. Mundra, Deputy Governor, RBI)
- Beyond loan appraisals, banks have to build teams that would do forensic audit of promoters' equity claims, and monitor the way funds are used and misused." (ET 21 June 2017).
- With times, banks have become wiser, and this has also led to an operationalization of credit information and thus the formation of the credit information bureau (CIBIL), which helps the banks to essentially perform background checks before lending. But, still it is not fully operational.
- Similarly, the central Repository of Information on large Credits (CRILIC) can help banks get more information about the history of corporate borrowers. But, it is again not fully used by banks to keep track of borrowers' activities.
- Banks can prevent promoters from gaming the system, if they begin sourcing data from institutions like CIBIL, which has live feed on defaulters.
- "Capitalism without financial failure is not capitalism at all, but a kind of socialism for the rich." (Uday Kotak, Executive Chairman, Kotak Mahindra Bank).
- "Big Borrowers may not see Karnas in Indian banks, but Shylock enforcing contracts." (M.C. Goverdhan Rangan, Sangita Mehta, ET 21 June 2017).
- Inability to assess the quality and capability of borrowers in the age of credit ratings speak voluminously about managerial inefficiencies.
- Banks are known to resort to window dressing and ever greening their assets accounts. But, such manipulated assets cannot generate real and sustained cash flows for the banks. Nor do such accounts get fresh advances from the bank in question. Banks at best facilitate and cajole such defaulters to pay up, thus facilitating adverse business cycles.

- “Schemes such as CDR and SDR had been primarily used to avoid provisioning for the assets rather than resolving them” (Viral Acharya, Dy. Governor, RBI).
- “After the financial crisis of 2008, there was a push in lending to infrastructure and capital goods sector. But, as economic growth faltered, demand slowed down and capacity became idle, crimping the ability of firms to service their debts. So dumping took place as there was no buyer due to a concurrent slow down in the global economy. No foreign buyers were available, further resulting in a decrease in exports. Loans, thus became NPAs for banks.

Forensic Audit prevents the generation of non-performing assets in banks, by unearthing discrepancies in financial statements, by verifying actual cash flow statements, bank statements, etc. For example—in a recent case, forensic auditors found that a company with existing, huge cash reserves had surprisingly applied for loans. Later, the company was labelled as a wilful defaulter.

Some Latest Cases of Forensic Audits Conducted in India in 2017

- *Economic Times* (04 August 2017) reported: “SBI led consortium of lenders ordered a forensic audit of Videocon Company to find out whether the company had floundered because of adverse business conditions or due to financial mismanagement. A forensic report will also give lenders a clear idea of the liquidity position of the company, whether there has been any diversion of funds, misappropriation of assets and non-compliance of any of the regulatory norms. That will help banks in considering debt restructuring of Videocon in the region of approximately Rs. 43000 crores.”
- *Economic Times* (12 July 2017) reports that GTL Company (Telecom Infra Co.) has come clean in Forensic Audit and now Lenders are set to pursue one time settlement (OTS) for restructuring their debt amounting to Rs.6000 crores.
- “MCX (Commodity Exchange) is set to undergo Forensic Audit”, reports ET, 05 April 2017.
- “National Stock Exchange (NSE) faces a second Forensic Audit of trading system, this time by Ernest Young.” (ET, 30 March 2017).
- “Members of Public Accounts Committee (PAC) of Parliament asks for Forensic audit of PSB defaulters.” (ET, 03 March 2017).

Statutory Audit or Financial Statement Audit will usually not aid in discovering asset theft fraud, because the objective of the financial statement audit is only to determine whether the financial statements fairly present the

company's financial position. For example: If an employee sets up a dummy vendor to siphon off company cash into his own account, the company's book will reflect the cash payment. Even though the transaction is fraudulent, the company's financial statements will accurately reflect this transaction as an authentic one and thus fail to identify the asset theft.

An auditor conducting a financial statement audit cannot examine every transaction in the company's business record and cannot be charged with not discovering asset-theft fraud. If the financial statements fairly state the company's financial position, the auditor would be justified in issuing an unqualified opinion, even though undetected asset theft fraud is present.

Financial statement audit (Statutory Audit), is done for assurance that the business's financial statements in all material aspects, fairly state the company's financial position as on a certain date. An auditor conducting a financial statement audit is charged with performing audit procedures to *discover financial statement fraud but not asset theft fraud, which is subject of Forensic audit. A forensic auditor will not express any opinion on the company's financial statement.*

Suspicion of Asset theft Fraud

Sometimes, a small business owner will mistakenly request an accounting firm to conduct a financial statement audit if he suspects asset-theft fraud. If we tell our audit firm our suspicion or the audit is to detect asset-theft fraud, it should recommend a forensic audit instead of, or in addition to, a financial statement audit. Ideally, a forensic audit should be conducted by a certified public accountant who is also a certified fraud examiner.

Financial Statement Fraud

Financial statement Fraud is the intentional misrepresentation of a company's financial position through the misstatement or omission of certain transactions or disclosures in the financial statements. Financial statement Fraud is designed to deceive financial statement users, such as owners, investors, creditors or others who rely on the financial statements to make financial decisions.

This type of fraud is usually perpetrated by company executives whose compensation is tied to the financial performance of the company or whose position is dependent on the company meeting certain financial goals. If we suspect, a member of our business's management team is "cooking the book", so as to speak, a financial statement audit is designed to detect the financial statement fraud.

Through their analysis, Forensic auditors convert complex financial transactions into simple ones for laymen like the jury or judicial persons who are not very conversant with financial data interpretation.

Financial Forensic Engagements are in following Categories

Economic damage calculation suffered through breach of contract like in case of Banking NPA where there is breach of contract between bank and borrower who has diverted the bank's funds elsewhere for purposes far removed from the original purpose.

Money Laundering: Business Valuation (like over-valuation of the project cost that is submitted to the bank in order to get sanction, so that it takes care of the promoters' margin money too, thereby making the financial stake of the borrower NIL.)

After fraud, they frequently involve the assessment of accounting systems and accounts presentation; in essence assessing if the numbers reflect the actual position.

Internal auditors (Statutory Auditors) go through the checklist, that may not surface the evidence, which the regulatory body is searching for while forensic auditors convert complex data into terms which are understood and accepted by the regulator as well as the court.

Forensic Auditors: Four, big accounting firms are on the panel of the Indian Bank Association (Umbrella Organisation of Banks) for audits of frauds in Banks. Besides, there are other 39 accounting firms, empanelled by the Reserve bank of India for the smooth operation of Forensic audits. "The number of, banking fraud cases, in the fiscal ending March, 2017 have steadily increased to 5076 from a modest 4235 in 2012-13." (ET, 18 September 2017, PTI Reports).

Financial Forensic Engagements are thus in the Following Categories

- Economic damage calculation suffered through breach of contract like in the case of Banking NPA, where there is a breach of contract between the bank and the borrower who has diverted the bank's funds.
- Money Laundering.
- Business Valuation (like overvaluation of the project cost submitted to the bank for sanction, which takes care of the promoter's margin money, thereby making the financial stake of borrower NIL).
- After fraud, they frequently involve the assessment of accounting systems and accounts presentation—in essence assessing if the numbers reflect actual position.

Internal auditors (Statutory Auditor) go through a checklist which may essentially not be capable of surfacing the evidence, which the regulatory body is searching for, while forensic auditors convert complex data into terms which are easily understood and accepted by regulators and the court.

Need for this Forensic Study

NPAs are a part and parcel of the banking business and this will remain thus till banks exist, but it should be under strict control. The level of NPAs depends on how the bankers handle NPAs efficiently. The forensic analysis will help the banks to find out the level of NPAs in each sector, their reasons, and also suggestions of possible remedial measures for real income recognition, asset classification and provisioning. The causes and effects of NPAs need to be analysed at micro level to find out the causes and effect of the NPA, contribution of various sectors in increasing NPA levels, etc. Therefore, the proposed study will concentrate on micro-analysis of NPA accounts from a purely forensic angle. The research findings from the proposed study will enlighten the stakeholders of the various banks. This will help in enriching their knowledge of risk assessment and credit management.

Need of Forensic Analysis of NPAs of Banks

Though the NPAs are accounting norms, they have a direct relationship with recovery of loans and increase in the profits of banks. Hence, NPAs are the major cause for almost all problems in banking. So, the NPAs needs to be analysed thoroughly at micro and sub-micro levels and find out the actual value of the net NPA, Gross NPA and also the causes of NPAs. Forensic Analysis of NPA in bank thus provides the answer about the level of NPAs under various categories, NPAs in various sectors, real causes of NPA, etc. Therefore, there is a real need for study, concentrated on analysis of NPA accounts in a scientific way and considering the forensic angle.

Based on the analysis of secondary data collected from various sources, it is concluded that the inefficiency of bankers in credit assessment and credit monitoring is the main reason for the generation of non-performing assets in banks along with political interference in granting of loans. Forensic audit reduces this problem and helps in containing the number of NPAs in banks.

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